

Execution - data collection form (excerpt) (control group)

Welcome to the activity on elicitation of context-aware features. This is a controlled experiment and the participation is anonymous.

Execution

Write down a requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task "CREATE A COMMENT" (i.e. "comment an existing post").

Please write your answer here:

List of contextual elements that are available for you to use:

Entity	Contextual element	Description	Values
User	<u>User</u>	The user who is using the app.	-
User	<u>Account type</u>	Account type (that the user uses to sign in the app)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OAUTH • FACEBOOK • TWITTER • GOOGLE • OTHER
User	<u>Role</u>	Role of the user in the app	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Admin of a group • Suggestion worker • Dorifunk support team • Normal (regular user)
Post	<u>Event start date/time</u>	Exact date and time when the event is scheduled to start. Only available when post type is "Event".	-
Post	<u>Author</u>	The user who is the post author	-
Post	<u>Creation time</u>	Exact date and time when the post was created	-
Post	<u>Day type</u>	Day type when the post was created	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workday • Weekend
Post	<u>Date/time of last comment</u>	Exact date and time when the latest comment of a post was created	-
Post	<u>Date/time of last like</u>	Exact date and time when the latest like of a post was given	-
Post	<u>Part of the day</u>	Part of the day when the post was created	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning • Noon • Afternoon • Evening • Dawn
Post	<u>Type</u>	Type of the post	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free talk ("Plausch") • Event • News • Offer • Seeking • Suggestion (when the user creates a suggestion a suggestion worker of the municipality receives it and can interact with the citizen)
Environment	<u>Date/time</u>	Current date/time	-
Environment	<u>Day type</u>	Current day type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workday • Weekend
Environment	<u>Part of the day</u>	Current part of the day	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning • Noon • Afternoon • Evening • Dawn
Comment	<u>Content type</u>	Type of the content of the comment. Only available when post type is "Event".	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification • Funny • Gratitude • Greeting • Interest • Lament-feeling • Motivation • Opinion • Positive-reaction • Praise • Question • Reminder • Suggestion

Is there still time? *

● Choose one of the following answers
Please choose only one of the following:

- YES!
 No, time is over

Write down another requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task "CREATE A COMMENT" (i.e. "comment an existing post").

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'YES!' at question '2 [!STHERETIME!]' (Is there still time?)

Please write your answer here:

List of contextual elements that are available for you to use:

Entity	Contextual element	Description	Values
User	<u>User</u>	The user who is using the app.	-
User	<u>Account type</u>	Account type (that the user uses to sign in the app)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OAUTH • FACEBOOK • TWITTER • GOOGLE • OTHER
User	<u>Role</u>	Role of the user in the app	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Admin of a group • Suggestion worker • DorfFunk support team • Normal (regular user)
Post	<u>Event start date/time</u>	Exact date and time when the event is scheduled to start. Only available when post type is "Event".	-
Post	<u>Author</u>	The user who is the post author	-
Post	<u>Creation time</u>	Exact date and time when the post was created	-
Post	<u>Day type</u>	Day type when the post was created	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workday • Weekend
Post	<u>Date/time of last comment</u>	Exact date and time when the latest comment of a post was created	-
Post	<u>Date/time of last like</u>	Exact date and time when the latest like of a post was given	-
Post	<u>Part of the day</u>	Part of the day when the post was created	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning • Noon • Afternoon • Evening • Dawn
Post	<u>Type</u>	Type of the post	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free talk ("Plausch") • Event • News • Offer • Seeking • Suggestion (when the user creates a suggestion a suggestion worker of the municipality receives it and can interact with the citizen)
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Environment	<u>Day type</u>	Current day type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workday • Weekend
Environment	<u>Part of the day</u>	Current part of the day	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning • Noon • Afternoon • Evening • Dawn
Comment	<u>Content type</u>	Type of the content of the comment. Only available when post type is "Event".	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification • Funny • Gratitude • Greeting • Interest • Lament-feeling • Motivation • Opinion • Positive-reaction • Praise • Question • Reminder • Suggestion

Is there still time? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'YES!' at question '2 [ISTHERETIME1]' (Is there still time?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- YES!
- No, time is over.

Write down another requirement that adds context-aware functionality to the user task "CREATE A COMMENT" (i.e. "comment an existing post").

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'YES!' at question '4 [ISTHERETIME2]' (Is there still time?)

Please write your answer here:

List of **contextual elements** that are available for you to use:

Entity	Contextual element	Description	Values
User	<u>User</u>	The user who is using the app.	-
User	<u>Account type</u>	Account type (that the user uses to sign in the app)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OAUTH • FACEBOOK • TWITTER • GOOGLE • OTHER
User	<u>Role</u>	Role of the user in the app	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Admin of a group • Suggestion worker • Dorifunk support team • Normal (regular user)
Post	<u>Event start date/time</u>	Exact date and time when the event is scheduled to start. Only available when post type is "Event".	-
Post	<u>Author</u>	The user who is the post author	-
Post	<u>Creation time</u>	Exact date and time when the post was created	-
Post	<u>Day type</u>	Day type when the post was created	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekday • Weekend
Post	<u>Date/time of last comment</u>	Exact date and time when the latest comment of a post was created	-
Post	<u>Date/time of last like</u>	Exact date and time when the latest like of a post was given	-
Post	<u>Part of the day</u>	Part of the day when the post was created	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning • Noon • Afternoon • Evening • Dawn
Post	<u>Type</u>	Type of the post	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free talk ("Plausch") • Event • News • Offer • Seeking • Suggestion (when the user creates a suggestion a suggestion worker of the municipality receives it and can interact with the citizen)
Environment	<u>Date/time</u>	Current date/time	-
Environment	<u>Day type</u>	Current day type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekday • Weekend
Environment	<u>Part of the day</u>	Current part of the day	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning • Noon • Afternoon • Evening • Dawn
Comment	<u>Content type</u>	Type of the content of the comment. Only available when post type is "Event".	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification • Funny • Gratitude • Greeting • Interest • Lament-feeling • Motivation • Opinion • Positive-reaction • Praise • Question • Reminder • Suggestion